

Organizational justice and motivation on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)

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Abstract

This research is to examine the influence of organizational justice and motivation on employee organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). This research was conducted at Bank BPD Tabanan Branch, Bali, Indonesia with a sample of 75 employees taken using the saturated sampling method. Data collection was carried out by distributing questionnaires that used a 5-point Likert scale to measure 11 statements. The analysis technique used is multiple linear regression. The results of the analysis show that organizational justice has a positive and significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) and motivation has a positive effect on organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). The research results support all hypotheses and indicate the positive influence of organizational justice on motivation on organizational citizenship behavior (OCB).

Keywords: Organizational Justice; Motivation; Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB); Organization; Employee

1. Introduction

Human resources are valuable assets owned by an organization, because the success of an organization is determined by the human element. Without employees, an organization cannot realize all the plans it has made, because in the hands of employees all of this can develop. If an employee does everything that is not driven by things that are profitable for him, but because the employee feels satisfied if he can do or help with something that is more important to his role, then this condition can be called organizational citizenship behavior (OCB).

Organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) is behavior that arises based on an employee's discretion and is carried out voluntarily and without coercion (Andriani, 2012). A number of studies show a strong relationship between organizational justice and OCB. The real Organizational Justice that companies need to prioritize is that employees must feel that they are treated fairly that procedures and results are fair. This fair concept includes several things that are of concern to companies, including the division of work, wages, rewards, treatment, and things that determine the quality of interactions within the company.

Pin the process of developing fair behavior, it is important to understand how to influence the scales based on justice, satisfaction, staff motivation and commitment (Ghaziani et al., 2012). Apart from organizational justice, OCB is also influenced by motivation according to the statement put forward by George and Jones (2005) that high motivation greatly influences the emergence of OCB behavior in companies where employees have good behavior, are willing to try and work hard and do not give up easily. are characteristics of OCB behavior.

Motivation is an indicator that can make a worker more satisfied in carrying out his activities. According to Luthans (2006) motivation is a process as the first step for someone to take action due to physical and psychological deficiencies,

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namely an encouragement shown to fulfill certain goals. Murti and Srimulyani (2013) conducted research on motivation which found that employees whose needs were not met could become a motivation for them to fulfill these needs.

Providing motivation to employees in a trading company is very important because employees have a very big responsibility in providing the best service to customers in order to achieve the company's profit targets that have been set by the company. This research was conducted on employees of Bank BPD Tabanan Branch, Bali, Indonesia. Bank BPD Tabanan Branch, Bali, Indonesia is a trading company operating in the textile and fashion sector.

2. Literature review and development hypothesis

Research conducted by Nwibere (2014) proves that organizational justice has a positive and significant influence on organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). Sani's (2013) research also states that organizational justice has a significant positive effect on OCB. Research conducted by Ince and Gul (2011) proves that there is a certain relationship between perceptions of organizational justice and OCB. Employees behave positively to contribute to organizational development and pay attention to their work when they have positive perceptions of organizational justice. Sportsmanlike and helpfulness are dimensions of OCB has the smallest influence on positive justice perceptions, the type of justice that most determines OCB is distributive justice.

Widyaningrum (2010) said that the influence of organizational justice on OCB becomes stronger if fair treatment can increase job satisfaction and employee commitment to the company. Meanwhile, research by Iqbal, Aziz, and Tasawar (2012) states that procedural justice has a strong positive influence but distributive justice has a weak positive influence on OCB. Based on the description above, the following hypothesis can be formulated:

H1: Organizational Justice has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)

Nawawi (2003) said that motivation is a condition that encourages or causes someone to do an action. Antonio and Sutanto (2014) say that successful companies need employees who are able and willing to do tasks that are not part of their formal duties. Robbins and Judge (2007) say that there is a drive that makes someone achieve their maximum performance. This drive takes the form of the need for achievement, the need for socialization and the need for power or influence over other people. Research conducted by Panggalih and Zulaicha (2012) shows that motivation has a significant and positive influence on organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). This shows that the higher the motivation, the higher the organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). Based on the theoretical basis and various previous studies, the following hypothesis can be put forward.

H2: Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)

3. Methods

This research uses a qualitative approach, where this approach is an approach used to research a particular population or sample by analyzing qualitative data with the aim of testing a predetermined hypothesis. The objects studied in this research are organizational justice, motivation, and organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) in employees who work at Bank BPD Tabanan Branch, Bali, Indonesia. The population in this study were employees of Bank BPD Tabanan Branch, Bali, Indonesia, totaling 75 employees. The sampling technique used in this research used a saturated sampling technique. The data collection method used in this research is and questionnaire. The analysis technique used in this research is multiple linear regression analysis to determine the influence between the independent variable and the dependent variable. The independent variable in this research is organizational justice (X1) and motivation (X2), while the dependent variable is organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) (Y).

4. Results and discussion

The analysis in this research uses multiple linear regression analysis techniques. Multiple linear regression technique is data processing where this technique is used to estimate the value of the dependent variable using more than one independent variable. The results of multiple linear regression analysis can be seen in Table 1.

4.1. Organizational Justice on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)

The hypothesis of the organizational justice variable on organizational citizenship behavior (OCB), the result was that H₀rejected and H₁accepted. These results mean that organizational justice has a significant positive effect on

organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). This develops research conducted by Nwibere (2014) proving that organizational justice has a positive and significant influence on organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). Sani's (2013) research also states that organizational justice has a significant positive effect on OCB.

Table 1 Results of Multiple Linear Regression Test Analysis

Variable	t value	Significant
<i>Organizational Justice</i>	3.278	0.002
Motivation	3.702	0.000
R square = 0.675 F Statistic = 61.391 Significance = 0.000		

Primary Data, 2023

Ince and Gul (2011) proves that there is a certain relationship between perceptions of organizational justice and OCB. Employees behave positively to contribute to organizational development and pay attention to their work when they have positive perceptions of organizational justice. Sportsmanlike and helpfulness are dimensions of OCB has the smallest influence on positive perceptions of justice. The type of justice that most determines OCB is distributive justice. Widyaningrum (2010) said that the influence of organizational justice on OCB becomes stronger, if fair treatment can increase job satisfaction and employee commitment to the company. Meanwhile, research by Iqbal, Aziz, and Tasawar (2012) states that procedural justice has a strong positive influence but distributive justice has a weak positive influence on OCB. The results of this research show that the Interactional Justice indicator has the highest average value, which means that the main tasks assigned by the company are in accordance with the employee's field.

4.2. Motivation on organizational citizenship behavior (OCB)

The hypothesis of motivation variables on organizational citizenship behavior (OCB), the result was that H_0 rejected and H_1 accepted. These results mean that motivation has a significant positive effect on organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). This develops research put forward by Nawawi (2003) which states that motivation is a condition that encourages or causes someone to do an action. Antonio and Sutanto (2014) say that successful companies need employees who are able and willing to do tasks that are not part of their formal duties. Robbins and Judge (2007) say that there is a drive that makes someone achieve their maximum performance. This drive takes the form of the need for achievement, the need for socialization and the need for power or influence over other people. Research conducted by Panggalih and Zulaicha (2012) shows that motivation has a significant and positive influence on organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). This shows that the higher the motivation, the higher the organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). Based on the theoretical basis and various previous studies, the following hypothesis can be put forward. The results of this research show that the behavioral direction indicator has the highest average value, which means that employees have good relationships between co-workers.

5. Conclusion

Based on the results of the previous discussion, it can be concluded that Organizational Justice has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB). This means that employees who are treated fairly in the place where they work will have a high level of Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB).

Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB). This means that employees who have high motivation towards the place where the employee works will have a high level of Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB).

Based on the results of the analysis and conclusions obtained, suggestions can be given as follows. The first suggestion is that Bank BPD Tabanan Branch, Bali, Indonesia should improve indicators of distributive justice where the rewards received must be in accordance with the tasks assigned to improve good relations between employees and the organization. Apart from that, Bank BPD, Tabanan Branch, Bali, Indonesia should also improve indicators of behavioral direction in terms of good relationships with co-workers to increase organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). The second suggestion is that Bank BPD Tabanan Branch, Bali, Indonesia should increase interactional justice indicators where the tasks assigned by the company are in accordance with employee abilities. Apart from that, Bank BPD Tabanan

Branch, Bali, Indonesia should also increase the Business Level indicator where employees must take the initiative to complete work in accordance with organizational standards.

Future researchers who wish to conduct related research are expected to consider other variables that have a relationship with organizational justice, motivation, and organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) such as job satisfaction and can conduct research on different types of work in several other large companies, so that Research results can vary which can enrich references about organizational justice, motivation and organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). Apart from that, future researchers can also carry out variations in data analysis techniques, using paths or other analysis techniques.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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